

PEDAGOGICAL ASPECTS OF TEACHING CHILDREN VISUAL ACTIVITY

Iftikhor Bakhtiyorovich Kamolov

Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Qarshi State University

iftixor.kamolov@inbox.ru

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17251020>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 14th September 2025

Accepted: 29th September 2025

Online: 30th September 2025

KEYWORDS

Visual activity, aspect, lesson, paper, plasticine, creativity, ability.

ABSTRACT

The article discusses the pedagogical and psychological aspect of the problem: in visual activity classes, children learn to observe objects that are the result of practical activity and lessons, as well as to compose stories based on drawings.

Introduction. In preschool educational institutions, teaching children visual activities is significant for its role in developing the worldview of the younger generation, enriching their thinking, and helping them understand the world.

Engaging in visual activities is considered an enjoyable process for children. In particular, the attractiveness of art tools—colored pencils, paints, markers, and colored paper—serves to enrich the children’s world. When introducing preschool-aged children to objects through visual activities, the following factors should be taken into account:

Children’s age characteristics. This is especially important in preschool education, as children’s attention, memory, and thinking correspond to their age stage. Considering how children perceive objects, the duration of their attention, the peculiarities of their thinking, the type of memory (figurative, logical, or abstract), and the level of development of abstract thinking is essential. It is also important to take into account the children’s level of knowledge when describing the characteristics of objects.

Literature Review. Children’s Interests. Preschool children’s interest in exploring the surrounding world is extremely strong, therefore in organizing activities it is necessary to take into account their curiosity towards objects. The subjective need of children to comprehend the external world helps to form motivation for lessons. Likewise, relying on the child’s aesthetic needs and their aspiration to perceive beauty in objects contributes to increasing the effectiveness of activities. During visual arts activities, children’s interests should be considered when choosing models, patterns, or colors.

Presenting simplified information about depicting objects. The depiction of objects and making them close to real appearance requires significant skill from the child. For this reason, it is important to present visual art concepts in a simplified way. For example, when introducing the idea of perspective or marking the horizon, the information must be simplified, since abstract thinking is not yet well developed at this age. While

presenting simplified knowledge, it is also essential to strictly follow the principle of visualization.

Integrating visual art with play, labor, and cognitive activities. When introducing children to objects and teaching them to depict them, it is important to integrate all types of children's activities. This is because it is difficult for children to maintain attention on one type of activity for long. Frequent alternation of activities and tasks during lessons ensures that children acquire more complete knowledge about objects and makes the process more effective and engaging.

The main goal of preschool institutions is to develop children's creativity through familiarization with objects. Engaging preschoolers in creative activities not only reveals their natural abilities, but also helps them form holistic and complete ideas about objects, provides knowledge about their history of creation and possible uses.

In preparing children for visual arts activities, it is necessary to explain the specific complexities of art, introduce them to objects, and provide information about the important features of each object.

The role of the teacher in familiarizing children with objects through visual arts in preschool institutions is invaluable. The educator must possess deep knowledge and high professional competence, continuously improve their skills, enrich their theoretical and methodological level, and rely on advanced practices.

The State National Program is aimed at fundamentally reforming the education system, adapting it both structurally and in content to modern requirements, and continuously improving its quality and efficiency. The preschool education program is designed to develop children's creative abilities and their perception of the aesthetic aspects of objects.

Effective social adaptation of children in preschool institutions during activities places great responsibility on educators. It is well known that during various types of visual activity such as application, construction, drawing, and clay modeling, children develop cognitive processes like analysis, synthesis, repetition, and concretization. At the same time, they learn to work in groups, coordinating their actions with those of their peers. Visual art activities organized in preschool institutions are one of the main means of artistic and aesthetic education of preschool children.

The effectiveness of visual activity is revealed only when all tools of aesthetic education (drawing, application, theater, literature, music, etc.) are used in an integrated manner. Visual art classes help children to become familiar with objects and fulfill the tasks of aesthetic education, while also awakening their curiosity. During lessons, children gain full information about the characteristics and properties of objects, which fosters an aesthetic attitude toward them [5; pp. 137–142].

In visual arts classes, children engage in practical activities, learn to observe the objects they create, and practice composing stories based on pictures. As they reach school age, children begin to explore visual arts more deeply, including painting, graphics, and sculpture.

During preschool years, visual arts activities not only involve drawing objects but also include working with clay and plasticine, application, and construction activities.

Research Methodology. During group visual arts activities, children learn how to properly use pencils and brushes, position drawings correctly on paper, and depict the characteristics of objects. This, in turn, develops their concepts of objects, drawing skills, and the ability to move their hands lightly and freely with rhythm.

When drawing objects of various shapes, sizes, volumes, and proportions, children acquire the habit of maintaining proper direction according to the object's function and adjusting their movements in relation to the object's scale. In preschool educational institutions, visual arts lessons also teach children to use learning materials and tools in an orderly manner, keep them clean, use the necessary materials effectively, and plan how to apply them. Such activities develop children's attention span and visual memory.

In the preparatory group of preschool institutions, children gradually acquire skills in drawing objects from observation, which continue to improve throughout general secondary education. In the early stages—particularly in preparatory and senior groups—children are guided through the sequence of drawing from real objects. They attempt to analyze the properties of objects, sketch their overall shape on paper, compare the drawing with the real object, correct mistakes, and strive to make the drawing resemble the original.

During visual arts activities, children practice analyzing geometric shapes, identifying their specific features, naming them, and recognizing their width, size, length, height, and the spatial relationships of their parts. Construction activities, in turn, help to develop children's skills in visual estimation.

In summary, visual arts activities organized in preschool institutions foster not only artistic and aesthetic taste but also children's creative abilities, thereby laying the foundation for school education. Through interaction with objects, children reflect on their unique qualities such as size, color, volume, and shape, while identifying similarities and differences. This process nurtures sensory development and promotes imaginative and visual thinking.

These activities provide all-around education: children express their knowledge of objects and their perceptions through their own creativity, analyze surrounding events, and experience excitement from their completed work. During the lessons, volitional qualities are also cultivated. Children learn to complete what they started, respect group opinions, express their own ideas to peers, help those in need, and share what they have with others. Moreover, in evaluating the outcomes of activities, they develop humanistic qualities such as fairly assessing the work of their peers, recognizing their achievements, and rejoicing in their success.

Analysis and Results. Visual activity is a type of activity that motivates children to work persistently toward their set goals. It is considered the primary means of aesthetic education for children. The elements of aesthetic perception include the ability to distinguish the size, color, shape, and spatial position of each object. Through perceiving and sensing the characteristics of objects, children gradually develop their aesthetic sensibilities.

As children explore objects more deeply—recognizing their forms, diversity, and colors—they begin to take delight in color combinations and discoveries. As a result, they acquire the skills to evaluate the qualities of objects from an aesthetic perspective.

Conclusion and Recommendations. By guiding children to observe objects and their surroundings, the educator can foster aesthetic feelings that shape children's ability to appreciate the environment and human labor appropriately.

Teaching children to make use of unconventional and didactic forms of depicting objects on paper helps further develop their abilities, which is a pressing task today. The independent development of children's representations of objects provides a foundation for the formation of observation skills and aesthetic thinking.

Visual arts activities organized in preschool institutions cultivate children's ability to perceive and comprehend objects in the surrounding world, while at the same time increasing their interest in this type of activity. Gradually, preschoolers begin to understand drawing, sculpture, fine arts, and applied decorative arts.

In organizing visual arts lessons, the role of the educator is crucial. These activities not only develop children's fine motor skills and drawing abilities but also foster the proper use of educational tools. Through didactic drawing games, children are introduced to the transition from commonly used everyday objects to those used by adults.

For preschool children, the skills and competencies of working with necessary educational materials—such as markers, pencils, pens, and brushes—as well as knowledge of various drawing methods, movement techniques, and the ability to show the proportionality of different parts of objects in drawings, are considered essential components of drawing technique.

In teaching preschoolers visual-technical methods, it is necessary to begin with the basics of drawing techniques. Elementary movements include drawing arcs, vertical, horizontal, straight, curved, and wavy lines. These activities help children develop independence in their movements and prepare them for drawing and writing in the future.

References:

1. Bola huquqlari to'g'risida konvensiya. "Bola huquqlarining kafolatlari to'g'risida"gi O'zbekiston Respublikasi Qonuni. – T.: Inson huquqlari bo'yicha O'zbekiston Respublikasi Milliy markazi, 2008. – 34 bet.
2. Mirziyoyev Sh. M. Tanqidiy tahlil, qat'iy tartib-intizom va shaxsiy javobgarlik har bir rahbar faoliyatining kundalik qoidasi bo'lishi kerak. – Toshkent: O'zbekiston NMIU, 2017. – 104 b.
3. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Shavkat Mirziyoyevning 2020 yil 24 yanvardagi Oliy Majlisga Murojaatnomasi matni. <http://uza.uz>
4. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2016 yil 29 dekabrda "2017-2021 yillarda maktabgacha ta'lim tizimini yanada takomillashtirish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida"gi PQ-2707-son qarori. www.lex.uz
5. Kamolov I.B., Ashurova T.E. Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida bolalarni tasviriy faoliyatga o'rgatishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari / O'zbekistonning yangi taraqqiyot

davrida ta'lim-tarbiya va ilm fan sohalarini takomillashtirish muammolari mavzusida
xalqaro onlayn ilmiy-amaliy konferensiya materiallari. – Qarshi, 2022. –B.182-185